

Mechanical System Design and Development of Smart Pillbox for a Therapeutic Robot-Based Ecosystem

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Abstract

Non-adherence to medication and medication administration errors are important and complex concerns. Each year, medication noncompliance is estimated to result in 125,000 fatalities and \$100 billion in medical costs. Additionally, drug errors affect nearly 7 million people in the United States alone. Smart pill dispensers have the potential to significantly reduce both non-adherence and medication mistakes. This article describes the mechanical design of a smart, portable and scalable pillbox capable of working in tandem with a therapeutic robot in a system of wearable sensors and electronic monitors. The pillbox utilizes a linear actuator, servo motor, and vacuum-based suction mechanism as its primary operating components to store, retrieve and dispense pills of various sizes, shapes and surface finish. Design of Experiments (DOE) was used to determine the optimal design factors in a cost-and time- effective manner. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to determine the main effects and interaction effects. The design was optimized based on the results and further modifications were made to the design for 3D printability. The optimized design was validated by testing a functional prototype. The results demonstrate that the proposed pillbox can accommodate a wide variety of pills with high precision and consistency. The paper's primary focus is on the pillbox's mechanical design, though an overview of the pillbox's electrical and electronic components was provided.

Keywords: Pillbox, Medication adherence, Patient compliance, Smart medicine, Product design

1 Introduction

The global aged population is growing, with the number of elderly people anticipated to double to 1.5 billion by 2050 [1]. With the increase in the ageing demographic, many chronic medical diseases such

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as diabetes, hypertension, heart failure and dementia are expected to spike, leading to an increase in the usage of prescription drugs [2, 3]. The median number of prescription drugs administered to adults aged 65 and older in the United States climbed from 2 to 4 over a 12-year period (1988-2010), while the percentage of those taking more than 5 prescriptions increased by threefold (from 12.8 percent to 39.0 percent) [3]. Furthermore, human longevity continues to improve as the standard of living rises, particularly in industrialized nations [4]. All of these factors are expected to exacerbate an already substantial and unresolved problem of medical non-adherence and drug administration errors.

Medication adherence is critical for achieving treatment goals, improving quality of life, and minimizing medical and other healthcare expenses [5-7]. Nonadherence to medication, on the other hand, causes patients to miss treatment goals, worsening their health and raising healthcare expenses and mortality rates [7, 8]. A widely reported statistic is that medication noncompliance costs the US health care system up to \$100 billion a year and accounts for roughly 11% of annual hospitalizations in the US [8-10]. Nearly 50% of American patients are reported to disregard a recommended pharmacologic regimen. Moreover, administering incorrect drugs is a problem plaguing the health-care industry across the globe [11]. After vehicle accidents, diabetes, kidney illnesses, breast cancer, and influenza, medication errors are the sixth leading cause of death in the United States [12]. The most common causes of medication errors include incorrect preparation, timing, dosage, inappropriate medication consumption, poor communication between patients and their doctors, wrong drug selection, incomplete prescription, and other human-related errors (e.g., adverse drug events) [13-15]. Overdosing or taking the wrong drug can have catastrophic consequences and raise healthcare expenditures. Medication mistakes, for example, are responsible for the deaths of 7,000 to 9,000 persons each year in the United States alone. The entire cost of drug errors is estimated to be in the \$40 billion range [13]. Adverse drug events (ADEs), a type of human error, is responsible for more than 3.5 million physician visits and 1 million emergency admission each year [16]. Furthermore, avoidable medication errors affect more than 7 million patients in the United States alone, costing \$21 billion each year [17].

In spite of the pervasiveness of this problem, and the extent of the cost, no major entity or organization has taken it on as a priority. Even though, multiple authors and researchers have suggested individual solutions for over several decades, none have proven to be effective. The majority of solutions developed so far are medication boxes with alarm and other reminder settings to notify individuals to take prescriptions on time. A brief summary of pillbox design and development is provided below.

2 Materials and Methods

On August 4, 1964 David Wagner first patented a pillbox. It was proposed in circular and rectangular configurations, with seven sections for each day of the week. In 1984, Baker et al. designed one of the first intelligent pillboxes using a similar design but with programmable magnetic cards and a pharmacy computer that works in conjunction with a locking mechanism on each compartment [18]. At the time of dosage, the drawer automatically unlocks and a light turns on to indicate that the medication is ready for the caregiver or patient to administer. Since then a wide variety of intelligent pillbox dispensers have been developed or proposed. While a detailed history of the evolution of smart pillboxes can be found in our previously published review paper [21], an overview of the innovative and pertinent literature on mechanical design is presented herein.

In 2012, Abbey et al. [22] developed a smart pillbox employing a simple light sensor to track the medication intake. The rectangular pillbox had seven columns and four UV-resistant transparent plastic drawers per column. The author installed an LED light at the top of each drawer that illuminates when it's time to take a dose. A light sensor in the cell's bottom confirms whether or not the drug has been

taken. This pillbox is also linked to a calendar-like interface that functions as a supervisory schedule. Minaam et al. [23] designed a unique pillbox comprising of pill storage, pill chambers and hollow cylindrical exit tubes with zippered sections along which pills travel. To dispense pills, all the holes on all the parts need to align. When the holes are aligned, a servo is used to drop pills from storage into corresponding compartments. Chambers are built to fit only one vertically positioned pill to ensure only one pill is administered. Two Arduino-controlled servos were used to control the pill dispenser's lid and intermediary component.

Tsai et al. utilized a design that has the potential to reduce the medication loading errors. The author proposed a pill dispenser with a rectangular base and multiple circular slots, each with an electric switch at the bottom [20]. To operate the dispenser, the user inserts the medication schedule specifications (MSS) into the dispenser's on-board memory card reader. When new pill containers are inserted into the sockets, the socket switch closes, instructing the RFID reader within the base to scan the tags on the containers and locking the container in place. The dispenser reads the MSS disk for pill information and the scheduling. When it's time for medicine, the pillbox dispatches a reminder, lights up an indicator around the socket, and unlocks the drug container.

Huang et al. devised a pillbox with vending machine-like dispensing mechanism [24]. The pillbox consists of a spring with a base plank. A servo motor turns a spring to push pill packages forward. The package is dropped at the entrance when pushed past the plank. Infrared sensors at the entryway record drug deliveries to SQL server through wireless serial port. An alarm is triggered and the caretakers or families are notified via Skype when delivery or pickup occurs. Pak et al. developed a scalable and remotely manageable pillbox comprised of medication cartridges placed in a Medication dispenser tray (MDT) [25]. The proposed pillbox can accommodate up to six MDTs. Each patient's medicines and regimens are remotely entered or modified by medical staff or caretakers. The dispenser uses the MCU to control all system functions, an LCD screen to display medication information and set schedule, MDT to store & dispense the medication, an alarm system to alert the user, IR sensors to track the number of pills, RTM to record the time and date, and RS232 serial communication module. When it's time to take medicine, the pillbox alarm sounds, and the correct medicine cartridge is dispensed.

Antoun and Kassem [26] used an Arduino board to connect the pillbox to a cellphone and used parallel rotary wheels each with seven sectorial compartments for pill storage and individually controlled by axially-coupled servo motors. Once approved by the user on cellphone, the pills are dispensed through an opening at the bottom. Alexan et al. used a similar approach of wireless communication via Digilent ChipKit Max 32, 802.11 WIFI shield for wireless communication, DS1375 from MAXIX as IC, and PIC microcontroller to store the medicine information [27]. Farcas et al. used a 2-Line LCD allowing the user to manually enter the schedules for the pills [28]. Othman et al. also used an LCD screen for user interface and cellphone connectivity and improved the design by adding a combination of infrared sensors, Arduino microcontrollers and alarm systems. At the time of dosage, an alarm goes off and notifies the user via popup notification on the smart phone. Then the user presses a button on the pillbox and the pills are dispensed to a drawer through a pipeline. An IR sensor tracks the number of pills falling out and stops the vibrator when the required number of pills are dispensed. A Real Time Clock (RTC) module provides information on time and date. All the inputs and outputs are connected to the Arduino Mega 2560 microcontroller. The Raspberry Pi B+ and vibration motor are indirectly connected to Arduino through the relay module. Chawla et al. used a similar approach but used a different design employing 3D printed cones and wooden dowels [29]. At the dosage time as per the medication scheduled entered by the user on an LCD display, cones rotate catching a single pill each time and using two wooden dowels to dispense it.

Despite the fact that many of these intelligent pillboxes featured a wide range of designs and innovative concepts, the majority of them remained prototypes and never entered mainstream applications. Lack

of simplicity, scalability, and notably feedback mechanisms are some of the reasons for the lack of success. Although reminders and other notifications were shown to improve drug adherence, they did not produce the expected results. There is no one-size-fits-all solution when it comes to the problem of medication noncompliance. When people with mild cognitive impairment, dementia, reduced vision, and mental acuity are included, the situation becomes much more complicated. Because the topic does not fit into the boundaries of any one discipline, an effective solution requires innovation derived from interdisciplinary teams.

A multidisciplinary group of scientists, engineers, pharmacists, physicians, ethicists, and caregivers at the University of Minnesota Duluth (UMD) are developing a holistic human-like social interface-based ecosystem to assist dementia patients with their medical needs. This ecosystem employs wearable and spatial sensors along with a humanoid therapeutic robot. It is our belief that building a human-like support environment around the patient with robust feedback mechanisms, many levels of accountability, and a seamless flow of information between caretakers, physicians, and family members has the potential to produce unprecedented increase in medication adherence rates. An intelligent pillbox is a crucial component of this ecosystem. This article discusses the mechanical design and development of the intelligent pillbox capable of functioning in this complex and dynamic eco-system.

3 System Architecture

The architecture of the proposed ecosystem in which the pillbox operates is depicted in Figure 1. As seen in the Figure, this system is made up of wearable and spatial sensors, a smart pillbox, a processor, and a therapeutic humanoid robot. An NVIDIA Xavier processor serves as the system's brain, connecting all of its components and interacting with the caregiver, physician, and family members. The patient's vital signs, including heart rate, blood pressure, and electro dermal activity, are monitored by wearable sensors such as smart watches and fall sensors in the shoes. In more challenging situations, such as with individuals with dementia, spatial sensors can be utilized. The CPU will receive data from these sensors at regular intervals. When it is time for medication, the pillbox will dispense the correct medication at the correct time and notify the robot via processor. The robot with visual autonomy retrieves the pills from the dispenser, identifies the correct patient among several others in the facility, and administers the medication. If the medication is not taken within the specified time, the robot will return it and notify the caregiver via processor. The caregiver can then assist the patient further. Similarly, if abnormal conditions such as high stress or high blood pressure are detected by the sensors, the processor alerts both the robot and the caregiver. If a particular pill is configured for the specified ailment, the pillbox will dispense the prescribed medication. The robot will deliver the tablets to the patient and use the data from the processor to interact with the participant. Using an interface based on a mobile application, the physician, caregiver, or family members can also monitor the patient's condition at any time. If the patient is in good health and does not require additional monitoring, he or she can opt out of data sharing.

Figure 1: Architecture of the envisioned holistic ecosystem with a human-like social interface

4 Development of Smart Pillbox

4.1 General Design Requirements

For the smart pillbox to work well inside the aforementioned ecosystem or independently, the following design requirements were identified: pillbox should be able to hold up to two weeks' worth of medication and five different medications. The pillbox should work with impeccable precision. The pillbox must be protected and lockable. The pillbox should be lightweight, modular and operate quietly. The pillbox should be affordable and 3D printable. The pillbox should be able to gather and store information on inventory level, medicine dispensing time, and medication collection. The pillbox should be equipped with a programmable interface for entering the medication schedule. The pillbox should be capable of wirelessly transmitting data to an external server.

4.2 Conceptual Designs

Initially, several design concepts that could meet the requirements were considered including claw-based systems, optical sensor systems, sliding systems, systems that use pre-sorted containers, and rotating wheel-based systems. Since claw-based systems are limited when it comes to handling small and smooth medications, it was not taken into consideration. Optical sorter systems showed great potential especially that a vast selection of optical sorter systems is available. However, the start-up and repair costs tend to be high for these systems along with high design complexity. Hence this system was not taken into consideration in order to keep the design simple and price low. Initially, equipment based on pre-sorted containers was investigated, but these systems are still highly susceptible to human errors. Hence disregarded. Figure 2 depicts some early pillbox design concepts. The final design was chosen based on simplicity, reliability, scalability, delivery speed, lightweight and ability to manufacture in-house.

Figure 2: Initial design concepts: (a) Pillbox rotating about horizontal axis showing one column; (b) Using pre-sorted pillboxes with sliding mechanism

4.3 Mechanical Design

The proposed smart pillbox is shown in Figure 3. Figure 3a depicts the exterior, whereas Figure 3b illustrates the interior components. The respective component names are listed. As seen in the Figure, the pillbox has a cylindrical top and a rectangular base. The cylindrical top of the pillbox incorporates a rotatable tray, five medication cups, a drop cone, a lid with a locking mechanism, handle, and a vacuum suction tip for collecting pills. The bottom of the pillbox acts as the enclosure for all electrical components, including the vacuum pump, actuators, and controllers, as well as the dispensing station where pills are collected in a container. As the pillbox is intended to be portable, a handle is located on the top of the lid, along with side sleeves.

Figure 3: Schematic illustration of the SPBD a) exterior parts and b) interior parts

As seen in Figure 4, the rotational tray includes five circular holes into which cylindrical medicine cups can be slid. Each slot has a unique tab that only corresponds to one specific medicine cup. The medicine cup is a cylinder with a screw-top lid. Each screw-on lid features a central aperture lined with silicone padding. The aperture provides access to the pills for the suction tip, while the additional support ensures that the vacuum tip is kept straight and cinched. The silicone padding is soft enough

to prevent the pill from falling back into the container as the suction tip extracts it. Each medicine cup can accommodate at least 40 large pills. The rotational tray and medicine cups, in addition to the other components, are expandable to accommodate additional cups and pills, respectively. The rotational tray additionally has a sliding guide to guarantee that each cup remains vertical as the linear actuator raises it. One of the circular slots in the rotary tray has a conical form and serves as a dispensing area. Through this cone, pills are dropped into the collection cup. The rotary tray rests on a thrust bearing and rotates freely with the aid of a DC motor situated directly underneath. The base of the pillbox is an electronic housing with dedicated sleeves for controllers, processor, linear actuator, and vacuum pump.

Figure 4: (a) A schematic of the upper case with XZ and YZ cross-sections to demonstrate the pill suction process and (b) an upper view of the rotary tray with numbered holes.

4.4 Pillbox Mechanical Operation

The pillbox is loaded and emptied from the top. To load or unload pills, the caregiver unlocks and opens the lid, removes the medication cup from the rotary tray, and fills it with the desired medication. At the time of dosage, the servo motor rotates the tray at a predetermined angle so that the cup containing the desired pills is aligned with the vacuum tip (reference location). The motor stops and the linear actuator is activated, extending the piston rod and pushing the medication cup upwards. The vacuum pump is activated simultaneously. The pill is attached to the tip by the force of the suction as it gets close to the tip. The processor is pre-programmed to monitor the suction pressure. An increase in suction pressure indicates that the pill has been successfully collected. The linear actuator then retracts, lowering the medication cup. The servo motor rotates the tray until the drop cone is in proper alignment with the vacuum tip. Once the desired angle is observed, the vacuum pump's polarity is reversed, and the pill is dropped through the hole and into the collection cup at the dispensing area. This procedure will repeat until all the pills scheduled for dispensing at that time have been distributed. Once all the prescribed pills have been dispensed, the pillbox alerts the Xavier processor, which in turn alerts the robot. The IR sensor records the time at which the robot retrieved and returned the cup. The system will also keep track of the pill count. When the cups require refilling, the pillbox alerts the caretaker via Xavier processor. To eliminate the possibility of error during the refilling process, medication cups were engraved with numbers. The numbering on the list of pills to be filled should match that of the medication cups. In addition, to prevent the error of misplacing medication cups in their designated locations, both the medication cups and the rotary tray holes were constructed with distinct sliding

guides. Furthermore, the numbers on the cups and the rotary tray holes should match (see Figure 4b). As will be discussed further on, another function of the sliding guides is to maintain the medication cups in an upright position as they ascend.

4.5 Design Development and Optimization

Initial prototype evaluations were only fifty percent successful. Some of the causes include suction tip's inability to grasp pills, suction pressure that is either too low or too high, as well as behavior pattern variations due to pill shape and size. Design of experiments (DOE) techniques were utilized to determine the optimal parameters in an economical and timely manner. Table 1 displays the factors and levels selected for the study. Figure 5 and Table 2 illustrate the images and dimensions of the pills, respectively. In addition to size and shape, these pills were selected with different textures. Two pill sizes with smooth surfaces and two with relatively rough texture. Figure 6 and Table 3, respectively, depict the images and dimensions of the suction tips. Figure 7 shows the cross-sectional view of the cups under consideration. A total of 128 runs with 10 replications were conducted. The vacuum tip must select the correct pill in the first attempt for the experiment to be deemed successful. If more than one pill is picked (especially at higher vacuum pressures), the experiment is considered as unsuccessful. The percentage of the number of successful attempts to the total number of attempts is considered as the response variable. The experimental results are then analyzed using the analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Table 1: Joint effect of shape parameter and mesh aligning parameter on error metrics

Factors	Abbreviation	Levels			
		1	2	3	4
Suction Tip Type	TT	Convex	Concave	-	-
Vacuum Tip Dia. (in.)	TS	0.094	0.125	0.16	0.2
Medication Cup Base Shape	CS	Flat	Concave	-	-
Vacuum Pressure Magnitude (in. Hg)	PM	10	15	-	-
Pill Size	PZ	Large A	Large B	Small A	Small B
Pill Shape	PS	Cylindrical	Tall with Edges	-	-

Figure 5: Different pills used in the DOE investigation

	A (Cylindrical)		B (Tall with edges)	
	Size (L × dia.) (in.)	Weight (g)	Size (L × W × H) (in.)	Weight (g)
(Small)	0.82×0.26	0.325	0.56×0.27×0.24	0.6762
(Large)	0.93×0.3	0.86	0.75×0.32×0.3	1.436

Table 2: Pill specifications

Figure 6: Different commercial tips used in the ANOVA investigation

	Vacuum Convex Tip (in.)		Vacuum Cup Tip (in.)	
Small	Hole dia.=0.094	Outer dia.=0.3	Hole dia.=0.16	Outer dia.=0.37
Large	Hole dia.=0.125	Outer dia.=0.39	Hole dia.=0.2	Outer dia.=0.58

Table 3: Tips specifications

Figure 7: Medication cups used in the ANOVA investigation (a) concave base and (b) flat base

4.5.1 ANOVA Results

The ANOVA results of the DOE experiment is shown in Table 4. The P-value for all factors except tip size (TS) are less than 0.05 indicating their statistically significant effects on the response variable. Multiple two-way interactions were found between the factors. 'Tip type (TT)' was found to have interaction effects with almost all the factors except vacuum pressure. Interaction effects between 'pill size (PS)' and 'cup shape (CS)' was found. Another two-way interaction between 'tip size (TS)' and 'pill shape (PS)' was also found to be significant. Three-way and four-way interactions were not significant and not shown in the Table as it makes the table very lengthy.

Figure 8: The main effects of the levels of the design variables on the first response variable

Figures 8 show the main effects plots. It was interesting to observe that increase in suction pressure didn't really translate to higher success rate. This is due to the fact that at higher pressures, the tip was grasping more than one pill. When the pill size is small, this problem became worse. With smaller tip sizes, the increase in vacuum pressure made it difficult to release the pill. To address this in the final design, a small opening hole was made in the tip and the polarity of the vacuum pump was reversed at the end of each cycle. Also, pills with smoother surface (type A) had higher success rates than pills with edges (type B). Pills with edges prevented the vacuum tip from attaching. Regarding the tip type, TT, the vacuum convex tip showed slightly better performance than the concave vacuum tip.

Also, considering heavy interactions of tip with almost all the selected factors, the tip design was thoroughly investigated. The length, diameter and the material type were examined via trial-and-error process. Commercially available solid and flexible tips were first tested. Flexible tips were found to be more desirable as they wrap around the pill surface facilitating better suction. Furthermore, in another

Source	Sum of Squares	Degrees freedom	Mean Squares	F-Value	P-Value
Linear					
'TT'	225.78	1	225.78	5.35	0.02
'TS'	153.12	1	153.12	3.63	0.06
'CS'	2812.50	1	2812.50	66.67	1.65×10^{-11}
'PM'	175.78	1	175.78	4.17	0.05
'PS'	850.78	1	850.78	20.17	3.03×10^{-05}
'PZ'	4632.03	1	4632.03	109.80	1.62×10^{-15}
2-way Interaction					
'TT*TS'	4163.28	1	4163.28	98.69	1.37×10^{-14}
'TT*CS'	225.78	1	225.78	5.35	0.02
'TT*PM'	3.13	1	3.13	0.07	0.79
'TT*PS'	1012.50	1	1012.50	24.00	6.88×10^{-06}
'TT*PZ'	800.00	1	800.00	18.96	4.91×10^{-05}
'TT*CS'	3.12	1	3.12	0.07	0.79
'TT*PM'	63.28	1	63.28	1.50	0.23
'TT*PS'	850.78	1	850.78	20.17	3.03×10^{-05}
'TT*PZ'	132.03	1	132.03	3.13	0.08
'TT*PM'	7.03	1	7.03	0.17	0.68
'TT*PS'	94.53	1	94.53	2.24	0.14
'TT*PZ'	175.78	1	175.78	4.17	0.05
'TT*PS'	0.00	1	0.00	0.00	1.00
'TT*PZ'	78.13	1	78.13	1.85	0.18
'TT*PZ'	200.00	1	200.00	4.74	0.03
'Error'	2700	64	42.1875		
'Total'	21921.9	127			

Table 4: ANOVA for the effects of selected parameters on the picking succeed

experiment, the flexible tip with a dangling end was tested and found effective in improving the rate of success of picking the pill in the first attempt. If the flexible tip with a relaxed end failed to pick a pill while going down, it eventually will push against the cup base and bend, snake to the sides, and suck the nearest pill. Since it is difficult to obtain commercial suction tips with the desired durometer, shape and dimensions, we designed our own tips, 3D printed molds and made suction tips at our facility via casting process. And Mold Star™ silicone from Smooth-On Inc., Pennsylvania, United States with durometer values of 30, 40 and 60 were tested. Silicone materials with a durometer of 40 worked best. Figure 9 shows the 3D printed molds and the final cast suction tips.

Figure 9: (a) Modified vacuum convex tip with mold; (b) Modified vacuum cup tip with its mold

From Figure 9, it is also evident that the success rate heavily depends on the type of pill (pill shape and pill size) under consideration. Since we would like the pillbox to work with different types of pills, we took a closer look at modifying the design factors that they are interacting which are cup shape and tip type. It was observed that there was higher success rate of picking the pill when the bottom of the medication cup is flat instead of concave shape. That is because the curved base tends to tilt the pills, especially the large, tall ones, which prevents proper contact between the tip and the pill surface. This further confirms the two-way interaction effects of cup shape with tip shape and pill size. Yet, 88% success rate is not sufficient. At low inventory levels, the vacuum tip fails to get hold of pills when using the flat base type cup. To address it, multiple cup designs were considered via trial-and-error process. The final design that gave 99% success rate features an inclined wall at the inner lower corner and a circular meshed flat base at the center. The inclined wall allows for sliding the pills towards the center when the number of pills in the medication cup goes low. The flat center ensures that the pills at the center are laid relatively horizontally so that the vacuum tip approaches the pills perpendicularly. The meshed structure at the medication cup ground is aimed to prevent the vacuum tip from sucking the cup and giving a false indication of picking success. This signal utilizes the current magnitude passing in the vacuum pump. When the vacuum nose is blocked, the vacuum pressure increases, and consequently, the current magnitude increases indicating the pill is attached. All these adjustments in the medication cup are proven to enhance the rate of success in picking a pill the first time. Finally, the lid of the medication cup was equipped with a flexible eyelet at its center to align the attached pill and exclude any other extra pills from passing through the lid entrance. Figure 10a is a schematic cross-section with dimensions of the newly designed medication cup and Figure 10b shows the elements of the same designed medication cup.

Figure 10: A schematic of (a) cross-section of the modified medication cup with dimensions and (b) modified medication cup components.

4.6 Electrical and Electronic Components

A 12 VDC Feedback 360° high speed servo motor from Parallax Inc. (Rocklin, CA, USA) with a maximum speed of 120 RPM and torque of 0.95 kg-cm was used to rotate the tray. The servo motor was selected for its lightweight, continuous-rotation, bi-directional servo features and its embedded encoder. Additionally, an inbuilt Hall effect sensor system offers digital angular position feedback, enabling the servo to turn to and maintain any angle. A 12 VDC L16 linear actuator from Actuonix Inc. (British Columbia, CA, USA) with a maximum speed of 32 mm/s and maximum force of 50 N was used to lift the medication cups. This actuator was selected due its light weight, high speed, low noise and relatively large stroke length of 450 mm. A small Micro 12 VDC air/vacuum pump from GTek Automation Inc. (Lake Forest, CA, USA) with brushless motor, good airtightness, low noise and better flow control that can apply vacuum up to -22 inHg was selected to apply vacuum. The system uses Raspberry Pi4 which is a 64-bit Broadcom BCM2711 quad-core processor with a ARM Cortex-A72 CPU as the master chip. Temperature and humidity sensors were used to monitor the conditions in the pillbox. An IR sensor embedded at the dispensation station monitors if the pill container is picked up by the robot and retrieved. A DS1302 trickle charge time keeping chip is used to set the time and multiple alarm features. A generic touch screen display compatible with the selected processor is chosen for the interface.

4.7 Results and Verification

The optimized design was further modified for 3D-printability (minimum material consumption and production time). All components of the prototype were 3D printed on a large format Raise3D Pro2 Plus 3D Printer (Raise3D Inc., Irvien, CA, USA). Polylactic Acid (PLA) XTR filament with 1.75mm diameter from Essentium Inc. (Pflugerville, TX, USA) was used. A 0.4mm nozzle diameter, 0.2 mm layer thickness, 20% infill density, 60°C bed temperature, 220°C nozzle temperature, 80 mm/sec. print speed and gyroid infill pattern with supports were used to print the parts. Figure 11 shows the printed

and assembled parts. The functional prototype loaded with the different pill types was tested 31 times and the ability of the pillbox to pick and dispense the right pill in the first attempt was evaluated. The pillbox successfully collected the pills with 99% accuracy. The device operated at low noise levels and at excellent speeds.

Figure 11: 3D Printed Prototype: (a) Assembled part including servo motor and linear actuator, (b) Rotary tray with supports for 3D Printing, and (c) Top view of assembled prototype showing the cups, silicone inserts and vacuum tip

5 Conclusion

The mechanical design and development of a smart pillbox capable of autonomously extracting and dispersing pills by suction pressure is shown. Statistical methods were employed to discover design features that would result in high accuracy in dispensing a variety of pills. The device can simultaneously store over 50 small and 40 large pills. This study demonstrates that the proposed design is capable of retrieving a wide variety of pills (various sizes and textures) with high precision. The proposed design was validated by 3D printing and testing the assembled prototype. The servo motor and linear actuator are both quiet, lightweight, and operate effectively. Additionally, the pillbox demonstrated that it is capable of communicating with the external Central processing unit. Electronics capable of rapidly changing the weight of the pills at the proper angles have been identified. Even if the cost is high for application in most houses at present time, it is more economically suitable for a hospital or institution since this system can serve numerous patients at the same time. In addition, future design revisions and simplifications may bring the price down to an acceptable level that is suitable for individual needs.

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